

Inhibitory activity of *Sandoricum koetjape* Merr. (Santol) leaf extract to Blood Type O fibrin formation

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluated the inhibitory activity of *Sandoricum koetjape* Merr. leaf extract to blood type O fibrin formation, in which warfarin (positive), negative control and different extract concentrations (50 %, 75 % and 100 % respectively) were compared. The computed F-value for the treatment was 238 with degrees of freedom 2.7. For replication, the computed F-value obtained was 3 with df of 2.7. The former F-value was significant at 0.5 and 0.1 level of probability and the latter was not significant. Results showed that 100 % concentration has the highest time of coagulation and replication was almost the same.

Keywords: *inhibitory activity, fibrin formation, coagulation, anticoagulant*

I. INTRODUCTION

Coagulation is the process by which blood forms clots (Finkel, Clark & Cubeddu, 2009). It is an important part of hemostasis the cessation of blood loss from a damaged vessel, wherein a damaged blood vessel wall is covered by a platelet and fibrin-containing clot to stop bleeding and begin repair of the damaged vessel. Disorders of coagulation can lead to an increased risk of bleeding or obstructive clotting. Coagulation begins almost instantly after an injury to the blood vessel has damaged the endothelium lining of the vessel. Cardiovascular disorders such as hypertension and thrombosis are well-known in adults including arteriosclerosis and congestive heart failure which is caused by problem in blood circulatory system as blood clotting disorders constitute a serious medical problem. Warfarin and heparin and an

antiplatelet agent such as aspirin are used in disorders of coagulation (Zehnder, 2012; Martin, 2009). Blood-clot strokes can also happen as the result of unhealthy blood vessels clogged with a build up of fatty deposits and cholesterol. The human body regards these buildups as multiple, tiny and repeated injuries to the blood vessel wall. So the body would react to these injuries, if you were bleeding from a wound. This responds by forming clots.

According to the 2012 morbidity and mortality chart book on cardiovascular, lung, and blood diseases, stroke ranked seventh for those people aging from 45-64 years and fourth on those aged 65 years and older in 2008. Heart disease was the third leading cause of death for those ages ranging from 25 to 44 years, second, for those ages ranging from 45 to 64 years, and first, for those ages ranging 65 years and older. Based

on the chart 2-14 and 2-15 of the chart book heart disease, stroke and chronic lower respiratory disease were the second, third, and sixth leading causes of death of Asian males and heart disease and stroke were the second and third leading cause of death among the Asian females. In an in vitro study of the anticoagulant activity of some plant extracts that the consumption of dietary anticoagulants which contain blood thinning activity can ultimately reduce or eliminate the risk of thromboembolic diseases (Al-saadi, 2013). The study justifies that there are traditional or plant extracts that can lower the risk of thromboembolic disease (Kumar, Joseph, George & Sharma, 2011).

Santol is credited for its numerous folkloric uses which are still used. Fresh leaves applied to the skin are sudorific, and used by the Ifugaos for diarrhea. Decoction or infusion of leaves used for baths to reduce fever. It is also, used for diarrhea and as a tonic after childbirth. Bark poultice used for ringworm. Bitter roots, bruised with vinegar and water, is a carminative; used for diarrhea and dysentery. Pounded barks applied to ringworm. Leaves used for skin infections and rashes. Roots used as tonic (Godofredo, 2013).

In everyday life, blood clotting is beneficial. Anticoagulants which are also called blood thinners work by interrupting part of the process involved in the formation of blood clots. This means that blood clots are less likely to form when they are not needed, but can still form when they are. Anticoagulants increase the time it takes the blood to clot thereby preventing harmful clots from forming and blocking blood flow, yet, can prevent existing clots from getting bigger. When you are bleeding from a wound, blood clots work to slow and eventually stop the bleeding. In the case of stroke, however, blood clots are dangerous because they can block arteries and cut off blood flow, a process called ischemia. An ischemic stroke can occur in two ways: (a) embolic; and (b) thrombotic strokes.

The study, through the wonder of santol may help in coming up with an option for combatting coagulation disorders specially to adults who may suffer and die due to complication. The study can likewise introduce a cheaper and more accessible anticoagulant alternative as the plant is locally found.

II. OBJECTIVES

The purpose of the study is to determine the inhibitory activity of *Sandoricum koetjape Merr.* (santol) leaf extract to blood type O fibrin formation. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Determine the onset of action (i.e. coagulation time) of the plant extract in terms of:
 - 1.1 50 % concentration,
 - 1.2 75 % concentration, and
 - 1.3 100 % concentration;
2. Determine the clotting activity of the blood plasma after administration of plant extract using clot test score; and
3. Compare the inhibitory effect of *Sandoricum koetjape* leaf extract to that of Aspirin (positive control).

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Preparation of Plant Sample. The leaves of *Sandoricum koetjape Merr.* was collected in Gullas Medical Hospital at the College of Medicine in Barangay Banilad, Mandaue city. It was authenticated by the Department of Agriculture.

Preparation of Leaves Extract. The collected materials were washed with water and dried on a shade. The dried leaves were crushed into powders and subjected to maceration for three days with methanol and occasionally shake. The marc is decanted to separate extract. Then methanol was evaporated through evaporating dish in a controlled temperature of heat.

Preparation of Experimental Blood. Three blood samples for blood type "O"

were taken from selected students of College of Pharmacy with healthy condition by using sterile syringes, withdrawn from vein of right arm and placed separately in a container containing trisodium citrate to prevent the clotting process. Each person was taken 9 ml of blood through Gullas Medical Hospital Laboratory. The blood samples then were centrifuged for 15 minutes at rate of 3000 rpm to separate blood cells from plasma in order to obtain pure platelet plasma for prothrombin time test. The obtained plasma samples of each individual were poured separately in plane containers using syringes and stored at room temperature.

Collection of blood and Plasma recalcification. 0.2 ml plasma, 0.1 ml of crude extract of different concentration and different volume of CaCl_2 (25 ml) were fused together in a plain capillary tube. For control experiment extract solution was replaced by same volume of 0.9 % saline water. The clotting time was recorded with stopwatch by tilting the capillary tube after every 5 seconds. This time is called the prothrombin time.

Clot Test Score. The tests were scored as (4+) where the fibrin clot fills the complete volume, (3+) where the clot fills more than half but less than the total volume, (2+) where the clot fills less than half the total volume, and (1+) where there is a little disorganized clot formation; (negative) no clot observed but little amorphous deposit might be seen. All of the tests were carried out in duplication.

Collection of Crude Extract by Maceration. Figure 1.1 Preparation of test plant by maceration, starting point is collection of leaves and dried under shade at room temperature and when all the leaves are dried then it is powdered and weighed 60 g submerged to 150 ml of methanol and macerated for three days, to make the leaves exhausted it is covered and occasionally shaken. After three days, the mixture was allowed to evaporate over an evaporating dish. The methanol evaporated

and left the crude extract of the leaves. Dried extract was stored at 20°C until used.

Research Flow. To enable us to start with the experiment proper, the collection of fresh leaves and collection of blood samples were being considered. First, fresh leaves were collected, washed and allowed to dry under the shade. When the leaves were dried, it was powdered and macerated with methanol for three days with occasional shaking of the container. Then, the solutions were separated from the powdered leaves; muslin cloth was used to totally get the extractives. The extractives were subjected to evaporation to get the solid crude extract. Second, blood sample were collected from healthy students with type O blood. The blood were extracted by a registered medical technologist in the hospital laboratory where the centrifugation of the blood sample was also done. The centrifugation of blood sample is one way to separate the plasma from the blood; the plasma was placed in another container. Lastly, the conduction of the experiment proper was done after the preparation of the crude extract with different concentrations. The control groups consists of the positive and negative controls. For the 100 %, 0.2 ml of plasma was added with 0.1ml of plant extract and 0.3 ml of calcium chloride. For the 50 %, 0.2 ml of plasma was added with 0.1 ml of plant extract and 0.1 ml of calcium chloride, and for the 75 %, 0.2 ml of plasma was added with 0.1 ml of extract and 0.2 ml of calcium chloride. As observed, the calcium chloride has a different volume in every different level of concentrations. After the administration of the extract to plasma, it was incubated in a water bath with 37°C and checked every single time. For the said positive control using warfarin a 0.2 ml of plasma was added with 0.1 ml of warfarin 5 mg and 0.3 ml of calcium chloride and instead of incubation it was tilted every 5 seconds.

Figure 1. Preparation of Test Plant by Maceration

Figure 2. Research Flow Chart

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The experiment was conducted for one week. After three days of maceration and occasionally shaking to exhaust the constituents of the leaves then evaporated in a evaporating dish to let the methanol evaporates, the total yield collected of crude extract out of 60 grams of powdered leaves is 6.66 grams. The yield was then divided into three sets of concentration containing 2.2 grams of the yield crude extract: (a) the 100 % then had an equal amount of 2.2 grams, (b) 75 % had 2.2 grams of crude extract the diluted to 0.7 ml of water, and (c) 50 % had then 2.2 grams of crude extract also diluted to a different volume of 2ml. In every concentration and trial, they were incubated to 370 °C in a water bath and checked after every 30 minutes and recorded for any changes.

Table 4.1 Determination of baseline coagulation time using saline solution for the control of plasma.

Test	Plasma (ml)	0.9 % Saline (ml)	Calcium Chloride (ml)	Coagulation times (minutes)
Negative control	0.2	0.1	0.3	1.0

The above table served as the baseline value of the blood plasma. This is the basis of the thinning time of blood after the administration of crude extract. As shown, the coagulation time of plasma before administration of plant extract is one minute.

Table 4.2 Determination of coagulation time using warfarin 5 mg to a blood type O.

Test	Plasma (ml)	Warfarin 5 mg (ml)	Calcium Chloride (ml)	Coagulation times (minutes)
Positive control	0.2	0.1	0.3	4.1

The above table serves as the baseline value for the positive control using commercialized warfarin. As shown, the coagulation time of plasma after administration of warfarin is four minutes and one second.

Table 4.3 Determination of coagulation time using methanol extract for 100 % concentration of crude extract to the plasma of type O blood

100 % Crude Extract Concentration				
Trials	Plasma (ml)	Extract (ml)	Calcium Chloride (ml)	Coagulation times (minutes)
1	0.2	0.1	0.3	4.35
2	0.2	0.1	0.3	4.14
3	0.2	0.1	0.3	4.26

This table shows that at 100 % concentration the blood coagulation is 4.35 minutes, 4.14 minutes, and 4.6 minutes which suggest that after the administration of crude extract until the time it coagulates there was thinning formation which could be comparable to the time results of warfarin.

Table 4.4 Determination of coagulation time using methanol extract for 75 % concentration of crude extract to the plasma of type O blood.

75 % Crude Extract Concentration				
Trials	Plasma (ml)	Extract (ml)	Calcium Chloride (ml)	Coagulation times (minutes)
1	0.2	0.1	0.3	1.8
2	0.2	0.1	0.3	2.0
3	0.2	0.1	0.3	1.9

This table shows that at 75% crude extract concentration the blood coagulation is 1.8 minutes, 2 minutes, and 1.9 minutes which suggest that after the administration of crude extract until the time that it coagulates there was thinning formation but as compared to the 100 % concentration, it has less time of coagulation.

Table 4.5 Determination of coagulation time using methanol extract for 50 % concentration of crude extract of a blood type O.

50 % Crude Extract Concentration				
Trials	Plasma (ml)	Extract (ml)	Calcium Chloride (ml)	Coagulation times (minutes)
1	0.2	0.1	0.3	1.2
2	0.2	0.1	0.3	1.15
3	0.2	0.1	0.3	1.23

The above table shows that at this point of concentration the coagulation time was at 1.2, 1.15, and 1.23 minutes. These values were comparable with the negative control and suggested that there was no thinning formation occurred.

Graph 4.1 Thinning time formations of experimental and control groups

By looking also at the graph (graph 4.1) it showed a visual representation of all the different concentration trial results compared with the positive control and negative control. It then directly show that longer time duration of coagulation was observed in 100 % crude extract concentration which has almost the same value with the positive control.

Table 4.6 Results of Multivariate Analysis plasma to different crude extract concentrations of 100 %, 75 %, and 50 % in three trials.

Crude Extract Concentrations	Trial 1 (minutes)	Trial 2 (minutes)	Trial 3 (minutes)	Coagulation time (minutes)
100 %	4.35	4.14	4.26	12.75
75 %	1.8	2.0	1.9	5.7
50 %	1.2	1.15	1.23	3.58
Total	7.35	7.29	7.39	22

The above table shows the total value for every trial which then used in solving F-test or two-way analysis of variance. As shown, the obvious highest time value was 100 % concentration which then suggests that at this point of concentration there is a probable blood thinning.

Table 4.7 Degree of Freedom with Critical Values of 5 % above and 1 % below.

df denominator	Numerator	
	2	2
7	9.58	4.75
	9.58	4.75

Above is a .05 level and below is .01 level. The computed F-value obtained for replication is 3. The tabular F (2,7) = 9.58 at .05 α and 4.74 at .01 α . Hence, the replication is insignificant. This means replication does not differ from each other.

For treatment, the computed F-value obtained is 238 and the tabular F (2,7)= 9.58 at .05 α and 4.74 at .01 α , thus the treatment is

Table 4.8 ANOVA Table on the inhibitory activity of *Sandoricum koetjape Merr.* (santol) leaf extract to blood type O on fibrin formation in three different concentration and three replications.

Source of Variance	df	SS	MS	Observed F	Tabular F 1 %	Interpretation
Tials	2	0.15	0.075	1.5	9.58	insignificant
Treatment	2	15.5	7.75	3.73.83	9.58	significant
Error	7	0.035	0.05			
Total	11	16.3	5.096			

significant. This means the treatment of different concentration of crude extract such as 100 %, 75 %, and 50 % really differ with one another because the time of 100 % crude extract is the highest time of blood thinning.

The computed F-value for treatment is 373.83 with df of 2.7. For replication, the computed F-value obtained is 1.5 with df of 2.7. The former F-value is significant at 0.5 α and 0.1 α and the latter, not significant. This means that the treatment of different crude extract concentration upon administration to the blood plasma really differs. Since these are the statistical results, the null hypothesis was then accepted.

V. Findings and Conclusions

The purpose of the study was to determine the anti-coagulant activity of *Sandoricum koetjape Merr.* leaves extract on type O blood plasma. We had specific aims to (1) determine the thinning formation of blood in minutes in relation to the (1.1) baseline mean value of blood type O which table 4.1 shows the coagulation time of plasma without the induction of plant extract is one minute which indicates that anticoagulation or blood thinning did not occur. On the other hand, (1.2) experimental group (1.2.1) blood type O with 100 % of crude extract concentration had a constant time of blood coagulation in total of 12.75 minutes. This suggests that after the induction of crude extract until the time it coagulated there is a thinning formation which is higher compared to the time results of warfarin, 75 % crude extract concentration with total time of 5.7 minutes. This also indicates that between the inductions of crude extract and the coagulation time of the plasma there was actually occurrence of thinning formation, and at 50 % crude extract concentration which has the lowest time among other concentration to coagulate. This indicates that the thinning formation at a total time of 3.58 minutes when the concentration is low compared to 100 % and 75 % crude extract concentration.

In comparing the viscosity of the blood plasma after administration of plant extract, the viscosity between the blood plasma of blood type O and warfarin containing plasma was based under researchers' observation, when blood plasma containing warfarin was more viscous than to plasma with crude extract. In graph 4.1 the two controls were compared, the time interval shows that warfarin based on observation was rapidly acting with short duration of time because coagulation was observed for at least four minutes. This is compared to the other control which has 0.9 % saline as negative control solution with one minute.

Therefore, at the baseline mean of blood plasma indicates the level of control for the preceding experiments where the time of coagulation was one minute. So, if the preceding experiment exceeds the time of control then there is a thinning activity of blood plasma. Thus, the positive control using commercialized warfarin gave a positivity at four minutes.

Among the three crude extracts, 100 % concentration has the highest probability of anticoagulation. Therefore, it could be used as an anticoagulant. The treatment concludes that the study was significant though, the results shown in the replication were not significant could be due to human error.

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